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Measuring Wideband Nonlinearity of Analog to Digital Converters

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Abstract. Measuring the nonlinearity of an analog to digital converter (ADC) is often limited by the nonlinearity of the test signal. A differential test signal that combines two comb spectra has been used to perform nonlinearity measurements that are not limited by the nonlinearity in the digital to analog converter (DAC) used to generate these comb signals. Each of the differential inputs of the ADC is connected to one of the comb signals with different frequencies and the ADC effectively sums both spectra internally. This ensures that any intermodulation products in the ADC output originate in the ADC itself. Harmonic related products of the comb spectra are generated by the two DACs and the ADC. The out of band spectrum shows the combined effect of both DAC nonlinearity and ADC nonlinearity and includes both harmonic and intermodulation products. Although the harmonics of each test signal are hidden in the comb spectra, the hidden harmonic distortion power has been shown to be orders of magnitude below the intermodulation power. An FFT plot of the ADC output in principle enables a noise power ratio (NPR) measurement to be made but this would be limited by waveform generator nonlinearity to less than 18 bits. Comb filtering removes the harmonic spectra and harmonic products from the output of the ADC. The intermodulation products, in band and also out of band, are thus revealed. In contrast to NPR measurements, the measurement of wideband ADC ENOB is not limited by the nonlinearity in the signal generator.

We present the characterization of an audio test measuring system /audio analyzer using this technique and sine waves. The nonlinearity of the DAC was measured as 18 effective number of bits (ENOB) and the internal ADC as 22 ENOB. The validated dual comb test waveform is then used to measure the nonlinearity of a 24 bit 2 M samples per second ADC.

Keywords—wideband, effective number of bits, precision audio, ADC, DAC, intermodulation

I. INTRODUCTION

Pure sine waves are commonly used for testing the linearity and resolution of Analog-to-digital converter (ADC) circuits as they can be made close to ideal. Using a Josephson Arbitrary Waveform Synthesizer [1], quantization harmonics are theoretically at -200 dBc (dB referred to carrier signal amplitude). However, the limited output voltage at our disposal (100 mV rms) makes it suitable only for ADCs that operate with small signals. Pure sine waves have the advantage that harmonic measurement equipment is available commercially and in standards laboratories to check the purity of the source. They also have the advantage that they can be described analytically with ease. As the ADC output signal is a sequence of digital words further analysis can be undertaken using well known algorithms such as the fast Fourier transform (FFT).

Although the FFT facilitates measurement of sine-wave signal to-noise and distortion (SINAD [2]) ratio, a wider range of tests are required to ensure that an ADC will be suitable for particular applications. The concept of an ‘effective number of bits’ (ENOB [2]) has been produced that allows its suitability to be estimated. Unfortunately, real life signals that have to be measured by ADCs seldom resemble sine waves.

Moreover, if the linearity of the ADC must be specified over a wide bandwidth, this can be very time consuming to determine and harmonics which fall beyond the measurement bandwidth may be lost or hidden by aliasing. Multi sine wave test signals have been developed to facilitate testing wideband systems. Digital communication systems often handle signals that are wideband and have a spectrum like that of pseudo random noise. Nonlinearity in a wideband digital communication system is important to minimise as it can introduce bit errors.

In order to measure wideband nonlinearity it is first necessary to select one of the standardised intermodulation test methods that have many tones covering the test bandwidth. These signals can be conveniently generated using a commercial arbitrary waveform generator but nonlinearities in the internal digital to analog converter (DAC) limits measurement sensitivity.

Fortunately there is a standard test method that overcomes this limitation by using two separate arbitrary waveform generators and synchronous comb filtering of the ADC results. This method produces a wideband ENOB which can be related to sine wave ENOB and has been referred to as an ‘Alternative ENOB’ [3]. Recent research into the feasibility of a true 8 digit voltmeter [4] is evaluating several ADC architectures through measuring non-linearity in both analog components and standard ADCs. The project is evaluating ‘ultra pure’ [5] sine wave sources for standard tests but will also be using a commercial two channel arbitrary waveform source for wideband measurement of Alternative ENOB.

II. MEASURING EFFECTIVE NUMBER OF BITS

In essence, ENOB compares the performance of a practical ADC with that of a perfect ADC of the same resolution in bits.

A. Practical measurements of ENOB

This requires measurements of amplitude nonlinearity represented by integral nonlinearity error, noise due to differential nonlinearity and quantizing error, and random or thermal noise due to clock jitter or active components. The basic definition of ENOB, or n_e is:

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$$n_e = n - \log_2(P_{\text{ENOB}}/Q_{\text{rms}}) \quad (1)$$

where

- n is the specified number of bits in the ADC
- P_{ENOB} is total rms error and
- Q_{rms} is the ideal quantization error.

As mentioned in the introduction, ENOB is measured routinely using a sine wave test signal. This is calculated from the measured signal to quantising noise ratio (SQNR) using a standard equation [2]. In this paper we are using both sine waves and arbitrary waveforms and the theory is covered next.

B. Calculation of Signal to Quantising Noise Ratio of Any Arbitrary Waveform

In [3] it has been shown that, for an arbitrary waveform of crest factor C in decibels, the theoretical value of SQNR in decibels for an ideal n bit ADC is given by:

$$\text{SQNR} = 6.02 \cdot n + 4.77 - C \quad (2)$$

As $C = 3.01$ dB for a sine wave, substituting in (2) we have the well-known result:

$$\text{SQNR} = 6.02 \cdot n + 1.76 \text{ dB} \quad (3)$$

When imperfections in the ADC are included, SQNR is replaced by SINAD. Then effective number of bits n_e is related to SINAD by:

$$\text{SINAD} = 6.02 \cdot n_e + 1.76 \text{ dB} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Or } n_e = (\text{SINAD} - 1.76) / 6.02 \quad (5)$$

Hence, in general, for any arbitrary waveform:

$$n_e = (\text{SINAD} + C - 4.77) / 6.02 \quad (6)$$

However, to apply this equation in a practical situation, it is not only necessary to devise an arbitrary waveform but also a way to generate it with accuracy and repeatability and to measure its SINAD with precision.

C. Practical set up for measuring wideband n_e

This aim was achieved in a consumer quality experimental set up [3], using a passive signal summing unit. This is depicted in Fig. 1.

More problematic was the need to provide sufficient isolation between the two DAC outputs to cope with both

Fig. 1 Consumer quality dual comb filter measurement system.

source and sink currents. The 30 dB attenuation selected for each arm of the passive network resulted in the ADC input gain having to be increased to compensate for the loss: not an ideal solution. PC based software generated 24 bit 48 kHz .wav files for the 997 Hz sine wave and the double comb filter (DCF) test signal: 'dual PRBS' test signals (two periodic interleaved comb spectra signals with different base frequencies generated from Pseudo Random Bit Sequences (PRBS)[6]). As two of the DACs were required to generate the DCF test signal the .wav file was set to stereo format. The EMU 1616M unit has a digital signal processor that enables .wav files to be replayed and generate the test signals while simultaneously capturing .wav files from the ADC. ENOB was calculated by importing the .wav files into analysis software provided by Signal Conversion Ltd [7]. This analysis software synthesises the two comb test signals and two matching synchronised comb filters. An in-depth numerical analysis of this process is presented in [3] but it is summarised next.

To ensure that intermodulation power is much higher than harmonic power, it is necessary that there are at least 100 spectral lines within the measurement bandwidth [8]. It is also important that these lines are constructed from two interleaved comb spectra. With only one comb spectrum, harmonics and intermodulation products will all fall on the comb spectrum frequencies. Having two interleaved combs ensures that the intermodulation power falls in the spectral gaps. A comb filter requires a delay value equal to the repetition period of the comb spectrum. Each comb filter response is obtained by subtracting its delayed output from its input as in (7). If the period of the oversampling frequency is represented by the unit delay of z^{-1} , a comb filter with p samples has a sampled data transfer function $H(z)$ of:

$$H(z) = (1 - z^{-p}) \quad (7)$$

This filter has in effect infinite attenuation at the comb frequencies so will remove all the test signal but will leave intermodulation products as they appear as a broadband noise like spectrum that fills the gaps. It has been shown [3] that the 'white noise' power lost by this filter is 3.01 dB. As the intermodulation waveform is noise like, this correction factor can be applied in calculating SINAD.

Sufficient precision in the selection of the base frequency for the comb spectrum may require a clock rate that is higher than the DAC clock rate of f_{dac} . To overcome this, the synthesiser uses a higher sampling rate (e.g. an oversampling factor R) of $R \cdot f_{\text{dac}}$ in the algorithm. This is followed with an $R:1$ sampling rate down converter to provide the test signal waveform at a rate of f_{dac} . As this is a sampled data system, one period of the comb must be an integer number of samples (p) of the oversampling clock.

If the synthesiser DAC and ADC under test (f_{adc}) have the same Nyquist rate ($f_{\text{adc}} = f_{\text{dac}}$), then a matching comb filter (following the ADC) can be implemented by first having a sampling rate converter to increase the sampling rate to $R \cdot f_{\text{adc}}$. This is then followed by a comb filter using a delay of p samples. Final measurements are made following an $R:1$ sampling rate down converter. If the DAC and ADC Nyquist rates are not the same, then the oversampling factor in the analyser (R') must be chosen so that:

$$R' \cdot f_{\text{adc}} = R \cdot f_{\text{dac}} \quad (8)$$

It is therefore essential that this test method is applied in a synchronous test system as this ensures that comb filter notches will match the spacing of the comb spectrum.

III. PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATIONS IN TRUE 8 DIGIT PROJECT

The initial phases of the True 8 digit project [4] required selecting commercially available components, ADCs, signal sources and measurement equipment.

In this work the experimental measurement system employed an Audio Precision (AP) model APx555 [9]. This was located at PTB in Germany. Practical work was undertaken at PTB and signal processing and analysis at Signal Conversion Ltd in Wales. The ADC module under test was an Analog Devices EVAL-AD4630-24 evaluation board [10]. This module is connected to a PC and has board control software to capture ADC data and display results. Capture of ADC data from the board is controlled via a digilent zedboard which buffers the ADC data and communicates with the PC. PC based software provides analysis and capture of the data to a file on the PC for later analysis. The two DAC signals from the APx555 were connected to the two balanced inputs of the ADC via an ADA4945-1 fully differential amplifier [11].

A. Generating DAC waveforms by using .wav files

As a first step, the performance of the DACs in the APx555 used to generate the DCF signal was determined. Tests were set up by first loading into the AP a .wav file that defines the waveform to be generated. Two waveforms with a sampling rate of 48 kHz were employed: a mono sine wave of 997 Hz rate and a stereo dual PRBS 24 bit DCF waveform. These are the same waveform files used in the work reported in [3]. It is important to note that the use of .wav files to generate the waveforms ensures that the digital code range in the synthesised waveform is applied directly to each DAC in the APx555. This ensures that the actual DAC nonlinearity does not vary with APx555 output voltage. However, the non-linearity in output amplifiers might vary with output voltage so we selected 17 dBV for loop testing with both sine wave and dual PRBS.

B. Exporting ADC data from the APx555

The internal ADC within the APx555 generates a 24 bit code and this can be exported in a .wav file. The actual input voltage range of this ADC is not required for this analysis. We have based our analysis on knowing that the ADC has a 24 bit code range. When a sine wave input to the APx555 exercises the complete code range of the ADC we define this as '0 dBFS'. This does not indicate the input voltage to the APx555. Similarly, if we synthesize a digital sine wave of 0 dBFS as a 24 bit wav file it will exercise the maximum code range in the DAC but not necessarily that of the ADC. As a reference for future measurements, we have set the APx555 analog signal range to 17 dBV for loop tests as this exercises most of the ADC code range.

C. Configuring the AD4650-24 board

a) For the AD4650-24 board we chose the output voltages from the APx555 so that they did not exceed 0 dBFS in the digital output of the AD4630-24. Analog Devices test software produced spreadsheet format files which were then stored on a server accessible by all project partners. These were analysed by Signal Conversion Ltd using its custom

software [7] and the results compared with those of the Analog Devices analysis software

b) The insight gained from configuring these early tests was a simplification of the test set up in [3] that obviated the need for an external summing network or amplification. This ensured that any non linearity caused by the two DAC output channels not being completely isolated from each other has been eliminated. It could now be implemented without custom hardware.

Testing of the AD 4630-24 device is still in progress but as part of the validation of the test system, the APx555 was configured for loop testing with the dual PRBS signal and the 997 Hz signal. These results are presented next.

IV. RESULTS

Fig. 2 DAC codes shown as waveform 997 Hz -1 dBFS.

A. APx555 Validation

With the AP in loop mode its internal arbitrary waveform generator was programmed with a 997 Hz 24 bit 48 kHz sampled sine wave from a .wav file. This wav file was synthesized to operate the DAC at -1 dB FS to provide less non-linearity. Its waveform is shown in Fig. 2.

This waveform was generated by the DAC and captured by the AP internal ADC sampling at 192 kHz. Spectral plots from the ADC are shown in Fig. 3 and reveal

Fig. 3 FFT plot of ADC codes with sine wave from DAC.

that the AP internal DAC is non-linear and harmonics limit the result.

In Fig. 3 the FFT measurements are over a bandwidth of 20 kHz with an FFT length of 262144 samples. SINAD is calculated from the ADC data with the ADC at 5 dB below its full scale range. The DAC is being driven at near its

Fig. 4 Analyser showing FFT plot with analog sine wave.

maximum code range by the sine wave data (-1 dBFS DAC amplitude). The results are:

- SINAD 110 dB ,
- THD 112 dB and
- ENOB for ADC and DAC combined is 18 bits.

Fig. 3 shows significant harmonics and in order to help decide if these are dominated by the DAC or ADC, a further test was made using the internal analog sine wave generator which avoided using the DAC. The FFT plot produced by the APx555 is displayed in Fig. 4 and shows that the harmonics are at least 20 dB lower in amplitude. The difference between the spectra in Fig.3 and Fig.4 is the signal source, so we can conclude that the nonlinearity of the ADC is much less than in the DAC.

THD calculated from this dBV FFT plot is 129 dB. This does not include ADC noise, and, simply on the basis of the THD the sine wave ENOB of the ADC is estimated as 21.1 bits at 17 dBV input. It is important to note that the FFT plot in Fig. 4 is in analog dBV so does not relate directly to our digital dBFS.

In Fig. 5, the time trace from the DAC codes that produce the dual PRBS waveform is shown. It is important to note that the time scale is expanded to show that there is a positive peak close to the DAC Full Scale Range (FSR). The FFT of these DAC codes is shown in Fig. 6 to demonstrate the digital filter stop band characteristic:

The Alternative ENOB figures were calculated by first importing the ADC 24 bit wav file from the APx555 into Signal Conversion ltd WinSATS software [7]. After applying comb filtering the resulting waveform for the nonlinearity error had the appearance and spectrum of random noise. Applying (6) with the test results we have calculated the alternative ENOB as shown in (9).

The measured crest factor of the test signal is 12.2 dB .

The measured SINAD is 104.3 dB .

$$\begin{aligned}
 n_e &= (\text{SINAD} + C - 4.77) / 6.02 \\
 &= (104.3 + 12.2 - 4.77) / 6.02 \quad (9) \\
 &= 110.83 / 6.02 \\
 &= 18.4 \text{ wide band (but noise dominated) bits.}
 \end{aligned}$$

The next stage in the processing of the DCF error waveform was to smooth it to reduce the amplitude of random noise. After smoothing, the FFT of the DCF error waveform revealed the periodic spectrum of the intermodulation signal. This reduced the power of the error waveform by 21.07 dB and results in an SQNR of $110.83 + 21.07 = 131.9$ dB without random noise. It can be compared with sine wave-based measurements of ENOB that are calculated only from the spectrum of the harmonics and any other spectral products above the noise floor. This is possible because FFT processing gain and averaging of FFTs can reduce the noise floor to below the level of the periodic signals. When measurements are made of the amplitude of the sine wave it may not be at the full-scale range of the ADC. In that case a correction factor may be applied to estimate the best case ENOB at 0 dBFS. In the case of the DCF measurements the ADC code range used was 1.6 dB below its FSR. If we apply this correction factor, then the best case ENOB for the ADC in the APx555 would be based on $131.9 + 1.6 = 133.5$ dB SQNR.

$$n_e = 133.5 / 6.02 = 22.18 \text{ bits.}$$

Which compares well with the analog sine wave dBV based

Fig. 5 Dual PRBS DAC codes covering nearly the complete FS range.

Fig. 6 Spectrum of DAC codes generating dual PRBS waveform.

estimate of 21.1 bits. More accurate sine wave based measurements of the ADC ENOB using an analog sine wave will first require information on how the waveform amplitude in dBV relates to actual ADC code.

In summary, these results show that DCF measurements of ADC ENOB are not limited by the 18 bit ENOB of the DAC.

B. AD4630-24 tests

First a 997 Hz sine wave (programmed by a .wav file to be -1 dBFS DAC level) from the DAC in the APx555 was applied to the AD4630-24. The linear x axis FFT plot in Fig. 7 shows the fundamental very close to the Y axis and also the noise spectrum. Linear frequency axis FFTs have the advantage that correct harmonic orders are easier to spot visually.

Fig. 7 FFT of DAC based sine wave testing AD4630-24.

Next, the dual PRBS two channel test signal was applied to this ADC using its balanced inputs to sum both spectra. This ensures that any intermodulation products in the ADC output are due to the ADC alone. Harmonic related products are generated by the two DACs and the ADC and fall on the same spectral positions as the test signal so are not necessarily visible in the FFT. These are removed by two comb filters during the analysis process leaving only intermodulation products. As outlined in section C and [3] in more detail, the total power generated by intermodulation with a large number of tones is several orders of magnitude greater than the hidden harmonic power so do not cause a significant error in the SINAD.

The combined spectra appear at the ADC output and the picture in Fig. 8 shows its noise like waveform.

The out of band spectrum of Fig. 9 (frequency window expanded to show signal spectrum) shows the combined effect of both DAC and ADC non-linearities. This spectral information could enable a noise power ratio (NPR) measurement to be carried out with appropriate signal

Fig. 8 Output of AD4630-24 with dual PRBS input.

processing. But it also clearly shows the problem of harmonics from both DACs, and possibly the ADC being hidden in the test signal and this would limit the NPR result. For the dual PRBS test, the two harmonic spectra can be removed by comb

Fig. 9 Spectrum from AD4630-24 with dual PRBS test signal. The scale of the vertical axis is 20.0 dBFS/div.

filtering and the test clearly reveals the spectrum of the intermodulation products (both in band and out of band).

These results were obtained with the AD4630-24 operating with its on board 2 MHz sampling clock and the APx555 running on its internal clock. The next stage in the experiments will be to synchronize both clocks. This will enable synchronous digital comb filtering to be applied to complete the Alternative ENOB measurement for the AD4630-24.

CONCLUSIONS

This paper has demonstrated that an improvement in the method of combining the two comb spectrum waveforms (needed to perform a measurement of wideband alternative effective number of bits) has removed the need for an analog signal combining network. An FFT plot of the ADC output in principle could enable a noise power ratio measurement to be made but this would be limited by the APx555 waveform generator nonlinearity to less than 18 bits. For the comb spectrum test signals, these two harmonic spectra are removed by comb filtering. This reveals the spectrum of the intermodulation products both in band and out of band. In contrast with NPR measurements there is no limitation in ADC wideband ENOB measurement by waveform generator nonlinearity.

This improvement was applied in determining the wideband Alternative ENOB of a commercial audio test set. In the next phase of the project, coherent sampling of the EVAL board and the APx555 will be implemented so that synchronous comb filters can be applied to measure the Alternative ENOB. It adds a new test method capability that provides wideband measurements of nonlinearity no longer limited by waveform generator nonlinearity. It has been an important development of the EU/UKRI project true 8-digit digitiser [4] as it offers an alternative to pure sine wave testing in metrology applications. It may also have wider applications in the testing of audio and other communications related test systems.

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